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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 2.3 – IDENTIFICATIONS OF PRIVACY REQUIREMENTS

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Executive summary

This document provides outcomes from Task T2.3, which extends the privacy-related work of Task T2.2. It focuses on identifying additional privacy requirements and relates to Task T3.1's objective of analysing users' perceptions of privacy and fair data use in the context of Extended Reality (XR) -enhanced technology. As one of the inputs, the document uses user-related findings of the Deliverable D3.1. The outcomes of the document will be used to formulate the guiding design principles of the Deliverable D7.4. The document begins by reviewing various privacy frameworks applicable in the XR technology domain. It highlights existing approaches to privacy in XR and emphasizes the importance of user-centred features in the design of privacy-respecting XR technologies. The summary then introduces the current European Union privacy approach, particularly the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and describes the practical privacy-engineering methodology used to gather stakeholder requirements. This section also details the development and use of a questionnaire within a contextual inquiry. The questionnaire aimed to understand the balance between privacy concerns and expected data usage by participants. In the subsequent chapter, the summary outlines the elicited usable privacy requirements that should be integrated into the project.

As the project follows the 'privacy by design' paradigm, the continuous work on further specifying and applying these high-level privacy requirements will follow within the framework of Work Package 3 (which includes the work on the privacy-related surveys Deliverable D3.3 and D3.8) and Work Package 7 (which encompasses Deliverable D7.3 and D7.6, the design guidelines and validation reports for privacy in both the first and final versions). The requirements will be incorporated in Deliverable D2.5 (Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification, final version).

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1 Introduction

In the context of the industrial sector, particularly in the realm of off-highway machinery, the integration of Extended Reality (XR) technologies presents unique challenges, especially regarding privacy. As industries starting to adopt XR solutions to enhance operational efficiency, training, and maintenance, it becomes imperative to rigorously assess and address the specific privacy risks associated with these applications. While operating, XR technologies are capable to collect a diverse range of data. This data can include operational parameters, environmental conditions, and even operator interactions. While this information is invaluable for optimizing machine performance and safety, it also raises significant privacy concerns. For example, the 'always-on' nature of these devices in prolonged industrial use can lead to the accumulation of sensitive data, not just about the machinery but also about the operators, surrounding personnel, and trespassers. It is also worth mentioning that in an industrial environment, the privacy implications extend beyond the individual operator to encompass the entire work site. For example, XR devices used in off-highway machinery might inadvertently capture data about other workers or proprietary processes, thus posing a risk to both individual privacy and corporate confidentiality.

Finally, as the collected data are entangled into the working process and can be used to assess workers' performance, the XR-extended data collection raises ultimate ethical questions about the balance between operational efficiency and the privacy rights of employees. In environments where XR technologies are used, every action, decision, and even momentary lapse can potentially be recorded and analysed. This level of scrutiny could lead to a culture of constant surveillance, creating a stressful and potentially invasive workplace environment. The ethical dilemma here revolves around the extent to which monitoring for performance enhancement infringes on an employee's right to privacy and autonomy.

To address these challenges, it is crucial to implement tailored and explainable control mechanisms over data collection in XR systems. Industrial XR applications should be designed to give operators and management clear insight into what data is being collected, why it is necessary, and how it will be used. This transparency is essential for building trust and ensuring compliance with privacy regulations. This deliverable summarizes the work carried out as part of Task T2.3.

The work aimed to specify and extend the non-functional requirements provided in Deliverable D2.2 (GNFR 5 - 9), dedicated to implementation of "privacy-by-design" approach to the technologies' development. In the Deliverable D2.3 based on extended literature review and conducted studies with stakeholders and end-users, we provide additional requirements to deepening and specifying set of requirements presented before.

We approached the problem as an intersection of legal, technological, and ethical workspace requirements. Via rigorous analysis of privacy-related requirements frameworks and XR and privacy literature (Chapter 2), current workflow and expected XR enhancements, we identified the main privacy-related pain points we need to address in the project.

This is intended to be a final version of the high-level requirements. The results of this elicitation will be used further in the project to inform the user studies in privacy, (Deliverable D3.3 and D3.8), as well as affect the considerations of Deliverable D4.8. The results also informed the Deliverable D7.3 and Deliverable D7.6 guidelines. Finally, the requirements will be assessed in Deliverable D6.7. The requirements will be incorporated into the Deliverable D2.5.

2 Methodological approach to privacy in XR-enhancements for off-highway machinery

2.1 Privacy regulations

2.1.1 OECD principles

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) privacy principles, established in 1980, are a set of non-legally binding guidelines focusing on data protection and privacy. They are designed to promote privacy and data protection in both current and future scenarios [21].

Unlike legal regulations, these principles primarily address privacy risks rather than the technicalities of data processing. They also aim to bring a level of uniformity to privacy regulations across different regions. The principles include [21]:

- **Collection Limitation Principle:** Restricts personal data collection and mandates lawful and fair methods, preferably with the person's knowledge or consent.
- **Data Quality Principle:** Ensures personal data is relevant, accurate, complete, and updated as necessary.
- **Purpose Specification Principle:** Requires specifying the purpose of data collection at the time of collection and restricts usage to these purposes.
- **Use Limitation Principle:** Limits personal data usage to specified purposes unless the person consents or the law requires otherwise.
- **Security Safeguards Principle:** Mandates reasonable security measures to protect data from risks like unauthorized access or loss.
- **Openness Principle:** Advocates for transparency in data practices and policies, including the nature and use of personal data and the identity of data controllers.
- **Individual Participation Principle:** Grants individuals' rights regarding their data, including access, review, and rectification.
- **Accountability Principle:** Holds data controllers responsible for adhering to these principles.

These principles differ from Convention 108, which originated from a European Council proposal focusing on data protection. Convention 108 is more narrowly focused on data processing and is legally binding among its members unlike the broader OECD principles [13,14]. Additionally, there are terminological differences between the two. The OECD principles have significantly influenced various global data protection regulations, acting as a benchmark for best practices and guiding principles in the field of data protection.

2.1.2 General Data Protection Regulation

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is an evolution of the earlier Directive 95/46, focusing on personal data protection within the EU [35]. This shift began in 2012 when the European Commission proposed reforms to update Directive 95/46, reflecting changes in technology and emerging challenges. After four years of negotiations, these reforms were finalized in 2016. The GDPR's primary goal is to modernize the EU's data protection framework, aligning it with new technological realities [44]. It also aims to foster growth in the digital internal market and establish a uniform data protection standard across the EU, which is why it's a regulation rather than a directive. The GDPR, effective from 2018, consists of 99 articles and 173 recitals, marking a significant departure from Directive 95/46. The GDPR interacts with other legal frameworks, including the ePrivacy Directive, the Data Governance Act, the Artificial Intelligence Act, the Digital Service Act, and the Digital Markets Act, forming a comprehensive regulatory network for digital data management and protection in the EU [35].

The GDPR outlines seven principal guidelines:

- **Lawfulness, Fairness, and Transparency:** Article 5(1) of the GDPR mandates that personal data must be “processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject” [35]. This principle means that personal data should only be processed with a legal basis, as outlined in Article 6(1). Transparency entails informing data subjects about the processing of their personal data, as specified in Articles 13 and 14, and ensuring they understand this processing [20,44]. Fairness implies that data processing should not negatively impact the data subjects [29,43]
- **Purpose Limitation:** In line with the OECD privacy principles, this guideline states that data should only be processed for specific, legitimate, and explicit reasons [35, 43]
- **Data Minimization:** Data collected and processed should be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed” [35]. This means only the minimum necessary data should be processed, protected with state-of-the-art technology, and access to it should be restricted [20,26]
- **Accuracy:** This principle requires organizations to keep personal data accurate and up to date, in alignment with the subject’s right to rectification under Article 16 [35].
- **Storage Limitation:** Personal data should not be stored for longer than necessary [35]. Organizations need to identify appropriate retention periods and processes for data deletion, relating to the “Right to Erasure” (right to be forgotten) under Article 17 [26]
- **Integrity and Confidentiality:** Also known as the security principles, they require organizations to implement various security controls (technical, organizational, policies, and processes) based on the context and risks of data processing. The GDPR emphasizes achieving the Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability triad and mandates prompt responses to security breaches [26, 35, 43, 44]
- **Accountability:** This principle holds organizations responsible for complying with all the above principles in their data processing activities [35].

2.2 Privacy Requirements Engineering

The field of requirements engineering has been increasingly focusing on privacy and regulatory data protection. Various scientific and engineering studies have been conducted to explore these issues and develop related tools and methods [4,5, 7, 8, 23, 31, 41]. These studies generally agree that there are differing views on what constitutes a privacy requirement. Software engineers often struggle to interpret regulatory (1) requirements, and privacy and data protection considerations are frequently overlooked in the early phases of software development. Further research indicates that the failure of organizations to systematically integrate data protection regulations into their software development processes leads to issues like the infringement of user rights, misunderstanding of requirements, and reputational damage [6]. There is also a lack of consensus among stakeholders regarding the definition, fulfilment, and conflicts of privacy and regulatory data protection [23, 41].

The GDPR advocates for “Privacy-by-Design and Default”, meaning privacy should be an integral part of information system design. This contrasts with findings that organizations often mismanage privacy design and erroneously consider it covered by security mechanisms [6, 23, 41]. Moreover, relying solely on Privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), such as encryption, does not fulfil all GDPR requirements, which include aspects like notice, transparency, and data subjects’ rights. The advisable approach to overcome these challenges is therefore that of eliciting privacy requirements. Various methodologies, frameworks, and tools have been proposed in the engineering field to help with this task together with the analysis, design, verification, and validation of privacy and regulatory data protection requirements. In THEIA^{XR}, after thoroughly analysing and comparing various frameworks, we decided to implement the LINDDUN framework. This decision was based on LINDDUN’s ability to identify privacy requirements early in the system design process. It also provides a platform for different stakeholders to consider various aspects of privacy, extending beyond just the GDPR requirements.

2.2.1 LINDDUN framework

The LINDDUN framework [47], developed by the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, has been a prominent instrument in privacy engineering for over a decade. Its widespread acceptance and recognition in the field are evidenced by endorsements from notable organizations such as ENISA¹, NIST², and the EDPS³.

It is also well-regarded in the industrial sector [10]. LINDDUN is a knowledge and model-based framework that employs data flow diagrams to identify and analyse privacy threats right from the early stages of development [47]. This framework has successfully identified, analysed, and documented various privacy threats. The original LINDDUN has a tree of privacy threats, with 100 identified threats (leaves). It offers systematic methodologies for analysing each threat, enabling the modelling of these threats and the implementation of appropriate mitigation strategies [47].

LINDDUN is a systematic and thorough approach but tends to be time-consuming and requires significant expertise. To address this, LINDDUN introduced LINDDUN GO, a simpler and more user-friendly methodology. LINDDUN GO narrows down privacy threats from 100 to 35, focusing on the most prevalent and serious ones. It also incorporates compliance aspects, particularly concerning data protection. Specifically, LINDDUN GO is in line with GDPR regulations, and its compliance approach is versatile, focusing on general data protection principles rather than specific regulations or articles [48].

2.3 Privacy-focused Research in Extended Reality

This section provides an update to the " Privacy Concerns in Extended Reality" section found in Deliverable D2.2. by adding new developments and discoveries in the field of privacy within extended reality that have occurred since the submission of Deliverable D2.2, with a particular emphasis on the latter half of 2023.

2.3.1 Privacy Concerns in Extended Reality

Current research in XR (which means Virtual, Augmented and Mixed reality) highlights several privacy and ethical concerns [2, 18, 22, 28, 38]. A predominant issue is the extensive user behaviour data generated by Augmented Reality (AR), which could be exploited without users' consent and lead to user identification [17]. Similarly, analysing the possible privacy leaks in virtual reality space (Metaverse), Huang et al. identify the group of risks connected to the immersive interaction and including the potential leak of biometric information [25]. Additionally, ethical concerns arise from the spatial constraints in virtual environments, potentially manipulating user choices and revealing frequented locations [9, 22]. Chiossi and Mayer, in their discussion on emerging physiologically adaptive systems in Extended Reality, emphasized the significant privacy risks associated with extensive physiological data collection. They advocate for a privacy-by-design approach and stress the importance of diligently obtaining informed consent to mitigate these risks [11]. Certain technologies, such as eye-tracking, improve the placement of virtual objects. However, these technologies also pose a risk of unintentionally revealing private user data, including their personal preferences and cognitive load, frequently without clear user permission. [15, 36, 38]. For example, Khamis and Alt highlight AR privacy and security issues, including the unintentional disclosure of confidential data, the complexity of obtaining informed consent, and emerging vulnerabilities for attacks [28]. A recent study emphasized experts' concerns in XR about the lack of user awareness regarding data collection, opaque practices by XR developers, and potential manipulative tactics by malicious agents, exploiting these issues and XR's unique characteristics [1]. Despite some studies suggesting limited user concerns over data privacy in XR, a persistent apprehension exists among users about privacy in augmented environments [3]. This concern could inform future research, using co-creation techniques with users and experts to develop effective privacy protection solutions. Similarly, the study of O'Hagan et al. showed users low awareness but high concern about AR headset activities, particularly those related to bystanders' data [33].

¹ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/>

² <https://www.nist.gov/>

³ <https://edps.europa.eu/en>

2.3.1.1 Frameworks for Accountable Privacy in Mixed Reality

Legal scholars have highlighted the importance of regulatory measures to protect users in XR environments [46]. Despite this, there are limited frameworks available for evaluating potential risks. De Guzman et al. [16] introduced a framework focused on identifying privacy and security threats in Mixed Reality. This framework incorporates various privacy model attributes, such as integrity, non-repudiation, availability, authorization, and authentication. Additionally, it covers aspects like identification, confidentiality, anonymity, pseudonymity, unlinkability, unobservability, undetectability, plausible deniability, content awareness, and compliance with policies and consent. The framework suggests safeguarding five key areas: data input, data itself, data output, user interaction, and device protection.

Another noteworthy approach is the XRSI Privacy Framework by the XR Safety Initiative [27]. This framework focuses on assessing privacy risks, informing users about these risks, managing privacy, and preventing privacy-related incidents in XR settings. It also integrates these concerns within the broader context of Human-Centric Privacy by Design. Moreover, the XRSI framework aligns its measures with major legal privacy and compliance standards like the GDPR and the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA).

Norval et al. assert that XR systems are intrinsically linked to their environment and user actions. This inherent contextuality presents significant challenges in maintaining transparency and accountability, as it's difficult to foresee and address potential issues. The physical nature of XR means that problems can lead to immediate and serious consequences, such as injury, property damage, or even more severe outcomes, which go beyond the usual data-related issues. As a result, it's crucial to focus on how XR systems can be audited. This involves being able to reconstruct or comprehend the system's behaviour and its context during operation. The authors developed and tested a framework with experts to assist XR system developers. This framework aims to facilitate the capture and management of data necessary for conducting audits and ensuring transparency [32].

2.4 Summary: Privacy Approach to Development of XR-Technologies for Off-Highway Machinery

In crafting XR solutions for the off-highway sector, data privacy emerges as a key concern. This domain requires a multifaceted approach to privacy. We begin by acknowledging established data protection laws such as the GDPR [35] and standards like OECD privacy principles. Also, we consider privacy-by-design approaches like LINDDUN [37]. Beyond these, it's essential to factor in the distinct attributes of XR technologies [40] and how they integrate into current workflows. A crucial aspect of XR privacy is the systems' auditability [32], meaning their ability to identify and evaluate privacy risks. It's also vital that privacy solutions align with the end-users, here being the operators of off-highway machinery, ensuring their engagement and control over their data.

Taking into account the regulative approach to privacy (EU GDPR), drawing from the Framework for Developing Transparent and Auditable XR by Norval et al. [32], and incorporating insights from de Guzman et al. [16] and the XR Safety Industrial Initiative [27] we have developed a questionnaire to identify privacy risks based on expert analysis (provided in Appendix A).

We applied the LINDDUN methodology, in its light-weight version LINDDUN GO, in the form of privacy-dedicated workshops. Additionally, leveraging research on user-friendly privacy in XR and Cyber-Physical systems [1, 24, 34, 45], and studies on privacy perceptions [12, 42, 49], including in XR contexts [3, 22], we identified two key factors for XR solutions in off-highway machinery:

- how users and stakeholders perceive the utility of shared data and
- the importance they assign to the privacy of specific machinery and user-generated data.

Based on the identified factors, we developed a guidelines for the semi-structured interview (provided in Appendix B) with machinery end-users, discussed in each use case. The triangulated data were used to make a list of the privacy requirements for the project.

3 Methodology

3.1 Privacy Risks Questionnaire

To understand how stakeholders perceive GDPR-related privacy risks and elaborate on the requirements that would mitigate the privacy risks, we created a "Privacy Assessment Questionnaire for XR-enhanced Workflow."

This questionnaire is inspired by the Data Protection Impact Assessment process, typically employed in later stages of system development. Its usual purpose is to ensure that data processing within a system mitigates risks through safeguards, security measures, and mechanisms for protecting personal data, thus complying with GDPR. It also considers the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and others involved [35]. However, we chose to use this process earlier as part of a privacy-by-design approach to encourage stakeholders to consider the privacy solutions they apply in the project.

Based on Article 35, Section 3 of the GDPR⁴ we request stakeholders to use a 5-point Likert scale to assess the likelihood of risks at any stage of the project and with any solution involved. This scale ranges from 1 (no risk) to 5 (high-risk probability). Referencing the enhanced use case flows in Deliverable 2.1, we pinpoint each technological modification and ask stakeholders to evaluate potential privacy risks associated with the implementation of these adjustments. For this evaluation, we have modified the standard questions used for DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment) in medical⁵ and scientific⁶ fields to suit the context of technology implementation. Post-evaluation, stakeholders are asked to explain how they think these risks might arise due to the implementation. Finally, at the questionnaire's end, we invite stakeholders to mention any additional privacy risks not already covered by the previous questions. The questionnaire is available in the [Appendix A](#).

3.2 LINDDUN GO Privacy Workshops

We applied the LINDDUN GO approach to better understand and identify privacy requirements. Our strategy combines a timed and flexible approach: we discuss privacy threats for a maximum of 10 minutes per card, using these cards to stimulate debate about potential threats in the still-evolving system design. To thoroughly explore and define these requirements, we conducted three focused privacy workshops (five hours in sum), with stakeholders involved in each use case. The goal of using LINDDUN GO was to foster active discussions and exchange of ideas among stakeholders. We recorded these workshops, with participant consent, for later review and information extraction.

During these sessions, we examined various risks identified by the methodology, particularly in relation to new technologies, and discussed strategies for mitigating these risks in the system's design phase. This approach helped expand the participants' understanding, uncover common challenges, and brainstorm potential solutions.

3.3 Semi-structured Interviews with End-Users

As part of our contextual inquiry involving end users (further details and outcomes of which are described in Deliverable D3.1), we have created and regularly updated guidelines for conducting semi-structured interviews. These interviews are designed to gauge end-users' perspectives on the utilization of current

⁴ https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/data-protection-impact-assessments-high-risk-processing_en

⁵ <https://www.dsptoolkit.nhs.uk/News/12>

⁶ <https://www.hw.ac.uk/documents/privacy-by-design-dpia-toolkit.pdf>

working data, their views on the sensitivity of this data, and the context in which they deem data usage and reuse appropriate. The latest version of these interview guidelines can be found in [Appendix B](#).

3.4 Notation for Documenting the Privacy Requirements

To document the privacy requirements we have elicited, we have adopted a natural language-based framework called EARS [30].

EARS is a framework that facilitates the writing of requirements and is easy and intuitive to understand by different audiences that may not have expertise in requirements engineering. The EARS framework categorizes requirements into five classes: "Event-driven, State-driven, Ubiquitous, Unwanted behaviours and Optional features" [30]. According to the framework, most requirements fit one of these categories, which is particularly useful for expressing high-level requirements. We have then proceeded to write our identified high-level privacy requirements into one of these categories.

4 Privacy Requirements

This section outlines the initial set of high-level privacy requirements introduced for the project. Given the project's current phase, these requirements are intended to direct its development.

Future efforts will involve more in-depth analysis and fine-tuning of these privacy requirements to the developed technology.

Code	Requirement (EARS)	Details	Why	Level in the project
PR1	The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing	The data flows of personal data need to be clearly identified: where is the data captured, processed, and stored, and what type of personal data is it? A comprehensive mapping of all the personal data being processed should be conducted.	It is crucial to identify the personal data being processed and to apply the appropriate measures and processes to ensure compliance with the GDPR. Additionally, this will aid in fulfilling other requirements like data minimization. This requirement is essential for all use cases to achieve GDPR compliance.	MUST
PR2	The use cases shall adopt a data minimization approach	Once the personal data has been identified, the different use cases should assess exactly which personal data they need to fulfil their goals.	Under Articles 5(1)(c) and 25 GDPR, data minimization should be the default setting for all systems. Additionally, data minimization is advantageous from a security perspective, as it reduces the number of assets at risk.	SHOULD
PR3	When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it.	Given the current development stage of all use cases, certain privacy threats have been identified. However, this list is not exhaustive, and new privacy threats may emerge. If this occurs, the use case team should promptly discuss mitigation strategies for these privacy threats.	Privacy threats can significantly impact both the design of the information system and the affected data subjects or organizations. If these threats are not addressed, there is a risk that a malicious actor could exploit them, potentially leading to data or security breaches.	SHOULD
PR4	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	Personal data should not be processed eternally and once it has fulfilled its goal, it should be deleted	This requirement based on the GDPR principle of data retention. and data subjects' rights.	SHOULD
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	AI models have demonstrated that they can exhibit biases, mislabel humans, produce errors, mislead, and be	The first principle of the GDPR states that personal data should be processed fairly. Additionally, the forthcoming AI Act in the EU imposes	SHOULD

		unexplainable. In this context, the version of the object detection algorithm should not act against the best interests of the stakeholders involved, including pedestrians who may be crossing and the machine operators.	several requirements, with a particular emphasis on fairness.	
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing about the use of this system.	The sticker should be visible and easily understandable. It must clearly inform data subjects that a camera, equipped with or without an AI model, is in operation. Additionally, it should provide details on where to find the privacy policy.	Transparency is a fundamental principle of the GDPR, and it is important that data subjects are aware if they are being recorded. Data subjects should also know where to access the organization's privacy policies and how to contact the Data Protection Officer.	MUST
PR7	Where UX-enhanced features are integrated into the system interface, there should be a clear method for users to opt in or opt out.	This will be an optional feature for the machinery. Machine operators will have the option to turn this feature on or off.	From the user's perspective, certain implemented features may feel more intrusive than helpful. Users must have the opportunity to opt-in or opt-out of these features.	SHOULD

Table 1: Privacy Requirements

4.1 Future Considerations about Privacy Requirements

Throughout our privacy workshops, stakeholders frequently mentioned that certain aspects discussed seemed too advanced for the current development stage of the THEIA^{XR} project. Elements such as the legal basis for data processing, data flow between the database and the system, and certain transparency aspects (though not all), as well as their impact on user experience, were identified as privacy requirements. However, many of these aspects were deemed to be outside the project's current scope. Moreover, this deliverable is aimed at providing of high-level privacy requirements. Therefore, a more detailed requirements elicitation and analysis is anticipated for future technology developments and systems,

There was a consensus among stakeholders that this situation should be documented and noted in the corresponding deliverable. In other words, future developments should take into consideration additional privacy requirements beyond those identified in this round. Consequently, we want to emphasize that the privacy requirements elicited and analysed for this deliverable are not intended to be exhaustive or definitive. In this context, future development of technologies in these use cases should re-evaluate and update privacy requirements, with a particular focus on a user-centred perspective.

5 Summary of Findings

5.1 Data Protection Considerations

The analysis reveals, that in all three use cases, the stakeholders have privacy concerns around the following areas:

Scoring and Evaluation Based on Data: Stakeholders recognize that the current workflow already allows for assessing operators' work in various cases. However, they are aware that with an XR-enhanced workflow, the data could be used for in-depth performance analysis, potentially influencing administrative decisions.

Systematic Monitoring: Planned features, such as 360-degree cameras, drone cameras, and thermal cameras at workplaces and on machinery, are viewed as tools for comprehensive monitoring of the workspace and operators' actions. Stakeholders also realize that surveillance of operation sites can be seen as systematic monitoring of public areas and this should be considered.

Large-Scale Data Processing: The XR-enhanced solutions will generate substantial data on vehicle behaviour and operator responses, including head-mounted and haptic solutions monitoring. Stakeholders recognize the privacy risks and the need to determine which data should be retained and which should be deleted during operations.

Matching Datasets: As data collection in the XR-enhanced workflow comes from various source, there presents additional opportunities to identify operators or trespassers at operation sites. Stakeholders acknowledge the need for measures to prevent undesirable data matching.

5.1.1 Technologies-specific Risks and Points for Consideration on the Following Stages of the Project

5.1.1.1 Object Detection Algorithm's Training

Technology partners intend to deploy object detection technology using thermal cameras in each of the three use cases. These cameras will identify trespassers, and AI algorithms will be used to enhance object recognition and potentially predict movement paths. However, there are concerns about personal data collection without explicit consent from those identified as trespassers. Another concern involves AI algorithms' being trained on real user data, complicating the process of obtaining consent.

5.1.1.2 Teleoperations-supporting Technologies

The concern in privacy-sensitive areas relates to remote operations in Use Case 2 for reach stackers. Stakeholders are worried about the risks associated with transmitting data beyond the vehicle and external data storage.

5.1.1.3 Behavioural Data Collection and Ethical Use

Several stakeholders raised concerns about privacy issues in the proposed solution. They highlighted the risks associated with generating and storing large amounts of behavioural data, which could be used to analyse operators' performance. The problems mentioned by the stakeholders in this regard included the infringement of the right to privacy and the effects of openly declared constant data collection on labour satisfaction and operator stress.

Additionally, throughout the privacy workshops discussions, participants specifically discussed in depth privacy threats that were not considered in the requirements on the current stage of the project development. However, they also brought up several key points for consideration in the later stages of requirements elicitation and system development/in the integration part of the post-project use of technologies. **These include:**

USE CASE 1:

- **Transparency in Algorithm Use:** It is crucial to ensure that individuals are informed about how algorithms are being used, particularly for transparency purposes. This is especially relevant in use case 1, where algorithms are employed for the benefit of the users.
- **Metadata and Privacy Impact Discussions:** There needs to be a conversation regarding the metadata involved and its impact on privacy.
- **Concerns Regarding Real-Time Object Detection Models:** There are concerns related to real-time object detection systems. Notably, if such a system detects a human, it will not automatically halt the machine. Instead, it will issue a warning or trigger to the machine operator, prompting them to take appropriate action.
- **Human-Computer Interactions in general:** The overall amount and nature of interactions between humans and the computer system needs careful examination.
- **Environmental Changes Impacting Data Frequency:** Changes in environmental conditions, such as a snowstorm, could alter the frequency and amount of collected data, which lead to risk collecting more data and store them longer e.g. for investigation purposes. Although these changes in data gathering frequency are justified from a security and functionality standpoint, they might have privacy implications, for example in this case we would like to collect detailed data about user's performance.

USE CASE 2:

- **Non-stop Data Gathering:** At the operational site, surveillance cameras are considered for capturing real-time data continuously. This raises questions about the effective management and handling of this data.
- **XR Data as Source of Additional Confusion:** Operators are already utilizing a wide array of systems in different vehicles, leading to a lack of clarity on how data collection works in each system. Introducing an additional layer, such as XR technology, may further complicate this scenario, increasing the likelihood of confusion and accidental data sharing.

USE CASE 3:

(in addition to the topics, discussed in the relations to Use Case 1, as they are mentioned as closely related)

- **Security aspects:** Security issues on the stage of post-project implementations and use.

5.2 End-Users Need for Data and Privacy

The analysis of end-user feedback revealed that users found the information exchanged during their interaction with the vehicle (from both user and machine perspectives) not only helpful during the operation but also potentially beneficial for future use. Users suggested that this information could assist in personal quality control from the operator's standpoint and contribute to ongoing learning and improvement of performance. Overall, operators view the balance between information collected by the vehicle and the benefits of using and reusing this information positively. However, across all three use cases, operators expressed concerns about the risks associated with this information being disclosed to management. They fear it could be used to evaluate their performance and influence decisions regarding punishments and promotions. Operators also highlighted that making performance information available to other operators could foster unnecessary competition, potentially compromising workplace safety. Therefore, from the operator's perspective, protecting data generated by the current or enhanced workflow from unauthorized access is crucial. Ideally, they believe the extent of information sharing should be under the operator's control. On the other hand, operators acknowledged the importance of sharing information in the event of accidents, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach to data privacy and safety.

Drawing from these findings, it is pointed out that it is essential to establish a tangible approach for the amount of data and levels of privacy controls from the operator's side. Additionally, it is necessary to develop a robust and multileveled consent framework. This framework would empower operators to have a say in

how their performance data is used, ensuring that their privacy is respected while still allowing for the critical sharing of information in situations like accidents.

The ethical approach to the data demands implementing a transparent and fair system for performance assessment based on the generated data. This system should be designed to use data in a way that supports constructive feedback and professional growth, rather than punitive measures. The operator should have opt-out options for participating in the assessment that way and be able to apply for alternative assessment options.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

Privacy requirements must be elicited and analysed from the early phases of the development of a project so that they can be included in the project's design. From a regulatory perspective, the European Union (EU) has emphasized the importance of protecting the human right to privacy and data protection through different regulatory bodies. One of the most critical regulatory regulations in the EU is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which sets out a list of requirements that organizations and information systems should satisfy. For the THEIA^{XR} project, part of the privacy requirements relies on using novel technologies and the privacy risks of these technologies. Given its current status, this deliverable seeks to document high-level privacy requirements for the THEIA^{XR} project.

To identify and analyse the privacy requirements, we have used different well-established methods to understand the needs of the different stakeholders. Namely, we adopted the LINDDUN GO [48] approach for identifying privacy risks and launched a privacy risk questionnaire based on GDPR risks between the partners and made the first round of analysis of end-users data and privacy needs. With this triangulation of methods to identify the privacy requirements, we aimed to cover the needs of the different stakeholders, ranging from regulations to users.

The work presented here will inform subsequent phases of our project. In the initial stage of requirements engineering, we developed guidelines for semi-structured interviews. These guidelines will serve as the foundation for creating privacy-related questionnaires for stakeholders (Deliverable D3.3 and D3.8). The defined requirements will play a crucial role in the system development and testing methods for Work Packages 4-6. Additionally, by establishing top-level privacy guidelines for this and future similar projects, they form the cornerstone of our Design Guidelines for Privacy and Security Assessment in Human-Machine Interaction using XR (Deliverable D7.3 and D7.6). The requirements will be also incorporated into the Deliverable D2.5 (Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (final version)).

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

AR	Augmented Reality
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PET	Privacy-enhancing technologies
XR	Extended Reality
GNFR	General Non-Functional Requirement
EARS	Event-driven, State-driven, Ubiquitous, Unwanted behaviours and Optional features
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act.

Appendix A: Stakeholders Privacy Risks Questionnaire.

1. Information regarding stakeholders:

- Please enter your first name and surname?
- Can you give a short summary of your responsibilities in the project?

In this questionnaire, we aim to evaluate whether the technologies we intend to use in the XR-enhanced workflow could potentially lead to processing operations considered "likely to result in a high risk," according to GDPR.

2. Do any of the envisioned technological solutions within the project's scope include:

	1 – Not include at all	2	3	4	5 – Certainly include
Evaluation or scoring, including profiling and predicting, especially from "aspects concerning the data subject's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements					
Automated-decision making with significant effect: (e.g., exclusion or discrimination against individuals based on automated-decision making)					
Systematic monitoring: processing used to observe, monitor or control data subjects, including data collected through systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area					
Sensitive data or data of a highly personal nature (medical data, information about political views or data relating to criminal convictions)					
Data processed on a large scale					
Matching or combining datasets, for example originating from two or more data processing operations performed for different purposes (which is exceed the reasonable expectations of the data subject)					
Data concerning vulnerable data subjects					
Innovative use or applying new technological or organisational solutions					

Please, provide some information (One-two sentences) about why do you think this risk can emerge and with which technology it can be connected).

3. Evaluation of potential privacy risks that may arise in XR-enhanced workflows

In this section, we request your assessment of potential privacy risks that may arise when implementing an XR-enhanced workflow. Please provide **details about the technologies you plan to use in the case** and **indicate your response based on planning technology**. If you identify multiple possible technological solutions presenting different privacy risks, please specify them in the feedback form.

Snow groomer cases

Snow groomer case 1.1a: Indicate to the operator that the system is activated (XR)

Please rate the possibility of each privacy risk associated with the technology **within the use case**

	1 - risk is not possible	2	3	4	5 - highly possible risk	Not applicable
Will this technology involve the processing of personal information? (Personal information is information about people who can be identified from that information or in combination with other information)?						
Will this technology involve processing confidential information that is not personal data (information received in confidence, information that would substantially prejudice intellectual property, information that would compromise public safety)						
Will this technology involve the use of an external (not consortium-member) contractor or supplier to process personal data or other confidential information (including maintaining IT systems and applications)						
Will use of this technology involve transfers of personal data outside of the partner companies (including cloud services)						
Will the use of this technology involve processing other high risk personal data (detailed profiles of individuals; information about work performance, salaries or personal life that would cause significant damage or distress to that person if disclosed).						
Will the use of this technology involve the collection of any new categories of personal information about individuals that we don't already collect in the previous version of the workflow						
Will the use of this technology compel individuals to provide personal information about themselves						
Will information, generated by this technology about individuals be disclosed to organisations or people who have not previously had routine access to the information?						
Will the use of the technology be perceived as privacy intrusive, such as in the case of utilizing biometrics or facial recognition?						
Will this technology involve the processing of personal information? (Personal information is information about people who can be identified from that information or in combination with other information)?						

Which technology are you planning to utilize for implementing this XR enhancement? Please specify instances related to the risks associated with the technology.

We asked the stakeholders fill the form according all the instances of technology enhanced workflow, identified in D2.1 (30 instances).

4. Additional privacy risks:

- Are there any additional privacy risks associated with the proposed XR solutions? Please specify the risks related to the involved parties whose privacy is at risk.
- If your answer is yes, what methods can be employed to mitigate the risks that may occur?

Appendix B: End-Users Privacy Risks Perception Interview Guidelines (version 3, November 2023).

1. Perception of privacy and generated data.

- 1.1. Can you describe your workflow in terms of which information you are taking from the vehicle and input to the vehicle (2 – 3 examples coming to your mind);
- 1.2. Do you see this data as valuable (usable) or not specifically important to your work?

2. Use and reuse of the existing data.

- 2.1. Would you be interested in reviewing or analyzing data such as videos of your performance or log files of your actions? How do you envision this benefiting you?
- 2.2. Are there specific aspects of your job where you think having access to detailed data could help you make better decisions or enhance your work process?
- 2.3. Do you currently have access to the data generated by your work after your shift ends? If not, would you be interested in having access to this data for your personal use?
- 2.4. Do you believe that having access to data about your performance might encourage you to modify your behavior or work habits? If so, how?

3. Perception of data and data privacy in context of performance and quality of life:

- 3.1. In what ways do you think the data generated from your work can be useful for improving your performance or efficiency?
- 3.2. Are there any concerns you have about the collection and use of your work-related data? For instance, do you worry about potential privacy breaches or misuse of this information?
- 3.3. How do you think the availability of work-related data could impact your relationship with your colleagues or superiors? Would it lead to a more collaborative environment or raise concerns about surveillance?
- 3.4. Have you ever faced any situations where access to work-related data would have helped you resolve a dispute or clarify a sequence of events?

4. Designing for privacy:

- 4.1. Are there any specific features or tools you would like to see developed that could help you better understand and utilize the data generated during your work?
- 4.2. Do you feel that there are certain types of data generated during your work that should be off-limits for analysis or review? If so, what are those types of data and why?
- 4.3. Do you imagine any type of your working data which should be additionally protected from unauthorised access?

5. Expectations and concerns about use of Extended Reality:

- 5.1. Have you previously used any Extended Reality applications? If so, could you please share more details about your experiences with these applications?
- 5.2. Have you ever experienced a privacy issue or concern while using Extended Reality technology? If so, what happened and how did it affect your perception of Extended Reality?
- 5.3. Do you ever consider use of Extended Reality technologies on your working place?
- 5.4. What are your primary concerns regarding privacy when using Extended Reality technology?
- 5.5. Are there specific types of data you would be comfortable sharing via Extended Reality applications/ not at all comfortable to share via Extended Reality applications? In home setting or in working setting
- 5.6. To what extent do you trust current Extended Reality technologies to protect your privacy? What could developers or providers do to increase your level of trust?